

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF SELENIUM METABOLISM AND OXIDANT-ANTIOXIDANT SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PANCREATITIS, COMBINED WITH HYPOTHYROIDISM

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Abstract

One of the relevant areas of work of modern medical science is the study of comorbid conditions, because in the daily practice of the doctor, it is possible to state a significant increase in the number of patients with wide-spread concomitant and combined pathologies of diseases of the internal organs.

Keywords chronic pancreatitis, hypothyroidism, oxidative stress, selenoprotein P

Chronic pancreatitis (CP) is a progressive inflammation of the pancreas which leads to damage to the structure and disruption of the functioning of the pancreas due to fibrosis. [1] Oxidative stress (OS), that occurs at the accumulation of high levels of active forms of oxygen, is an important feature of various pathologies. OS is a pathological factor in the activation of the stellate cells of the pancreas, which leads to the deposition of collagen extracellular matrix, which causes fibrosis of the pancreas. [2] Patients with CP have a lower level of antioxidants and increased activity of free radicals, compared to the healthy adults, and increased regulation of reaction genes for stress in CP. [3,4,5,6] Essential selenium is a microelement, which occurs an important role in many biochemical processes of the human body. The importance of selenium in the synthesis of thyroid hormones was discovered in the 1990. When conducting scientific research, it was determined that the concentration of selenium in the thyroid gland was higher than in other tissues of the body. Selenium is part of the structure of certain proteins named selenoproteins. Approximately 25 selenoproteins contain selenium as an important structural component in the form of selenocysteine. [7] Half of all selenoproteins are selenoenzymes which necessary to regulate or repair oxidative damage, performing antioxidant function, while others play the role of a catalyst for the synthesis of the active form of thyroid hormone. Also it's necessary for calcium and protein metabolisms, etc.

Purpose: to study the state of the oxidant-antioxidant system and the level of selenoprotein P (SEP) in patients with CP is combined with hypothyroidism.

Material and research methods. 63 people were examined, 24 of them with chronic pancreatitis (group 1), 15 practically healthy persons (group 2), 24 patients with chronic pancreatitis with hypothyroidism (group 3).

The level of SEPP was determined by the immunoassay method "ELISA" (firm. DRG, USA). The state of the oxidant-antioxidant system and lipid peroxidation were evaluated by determining the content of malonaldehyde in blood plasma (MA PL.) and in erythrocytes (MA ER.), level of reduced glutathione (RG), glutathione peroxidase (GP) and glutathione-S-transferase (GT) as well. The acts of enzymes were calculated on 1 gram of hemoglobin (HB).

Results. The analysis of the obtained results revealed clear patterns of changes in the state of the oxidant-antioxidant system and lipid peroxidation in patients with CP combined with hypothyroidism. Disorders of lipid peroxidation in patients with comorbid pathology are determined, compared to a group of practically healthy persons, which is accompanied by an increase the in content of MA ER. by 68.02 % and MA PL content by 66.57 %; Oxidant-antioxidant system: decrease RG in blood by 2.39 times, against the background of compensatory increase in GP by 67.09 % and GT by 73.79 %. When comparing the SEP level in group 1 by 18.42 % SEPP level is higher than in group 2, and in group 3 by 31.11 % higher than in 1 group.

MA content of blood plasma and MA in erythrocytes, RG, SEPP level and antioxidant enzyme activity in the blood of patients with CP, combined with hypothyroidism

Groups	Ma in erythrocytes (µm/l)	Ma in blood plasma (µm/l)	RG (mmol/l)	GP RG per 1 gram HB for 1 min	GT RG per 1 gram HB for 1 min	Sepp mg/l
Patients with CP (Group 1) (n = 24)	8,13± 0,31*	2,39± 0,22*	0,71± 0,21*	213,60± 0,28*	137,18± 0,15*	4,5± 0,28
CP patients are combined with hypothyroidism (Group 3) (n = 24)	9,38± 0,33*/**	3,38± 0,61*/**	0,38± 0,72*/**	263,29± 0,32*/**	157,51± 0,94*/**	3,8± 0,19
Almost healthy persons (Group 2) (n = 15)	6,38± 0,29	2,25± 0,17	0,91± 0,09	176,63± 0,69	116,22± 0,91	5,9± 0,31

n - the number of patients in the subgroup; * - the likelihood of changes in almost healthy persons; ** - the likelihood of changes between a group of patients with CP and a group of patients with CP in combination with hypothyroidism;

Conclusions. Under the conditions of comorbidity of CP and hypothyroidism, there is a decrease of functioning of the oxidant-antioxidant system and lipid peroxidation which is characterized by a significant increase in the content of MA ER., MA PL. and decrease level of RG and SEP on the background of compensatory increase level activity of GP and GT, which complicates the course of the underlying disease, its diagnosis and treatment. The development of oxidative stress occurs more intensively in the comorbid course of CP and hypothyroidism. A complex pharmacological effect on the pathophysiological course and correction of oxidative stress will allow to improve the treatment of such patients and avoid complications in the future.

References:

1. Philippa M, Lin HJ. TRPM2 channel-mediated cell death: An important mechanism linking oxidative stress-inducing pathological factors to associated pathological conditions. *Redox Biol* 2020;37:1017-55 [PubMed]
2. Greg GK, Reza FA, Shiri L, Hirohito I. Reducing Pancreatic Fibrosis Using Antioxidant Therapy Targeting Nrf 2 Antioxidant Pathway: A Possible Treatment for Chronic Pancreatitis. *Pancreas* 2019;48(10):1259-1262. [PubMed]
3. Singh N, Bhardwaj P, Pandey RM, Saraya A. Oxidative stress and antioxidant capacity in patients with chronic pancreatitis with and without diabetes mellitus. *Indian J. Gastroenterol.* 2012; 31: 226–31. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Tandon RK, Garg PK. Oxidative stress in chronic pancreatitis: pathophysiological relevance and management. *Antioxid. Redox Signal.* 2011; 15: 2757–66. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
5. Bopanna S, Nayak B, Prakash S, null S, Mahapatra SJ, Garg PK. Increased oxidative stress and deficient antioxidant levels may be involved in the pathogenesis of idiopathic recurrent acute pancreatitis. *Pancreatol.* 2017; 17: 529–33. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
6. Fu K, Sarras MP, De Lisle RC, Andrews GK. Expression of oxidative stress-responsive genes and cytokine genes during caerulein-induced acute pancreatitis. *Am. J. Physiol.* 1997; 273 (3 Pt 1): G696–705. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
7. Winther KH, Rayman MP, Bonnema SJ, Hegedüs L. Selenium in thyroid disorders - essential knowledge for clinicians. *Nat Rev Endocrinol.* 2020 Mar;16(3):165-176. doi: 10.1038/s41574-019-0311-6. Epub 2020 Jan 30. PMID: 32001830.